

Important factors to remember when constructing a cross-site scripting prevention mechanism

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ABSTRACT

Web application has become an essential part of daily activities to provide easy accessibility that ensures better performance. It is a platform where sensitive information such as username, password, credit card details, operating system and software version. is stored that attracts intruders to generate most of their attacks. Intruders can steal valuable data by compromising web application security flaws; cross site scripting (XSS) vulnerability is one of these. Several studies have been conducted in order to prevent the XSS vulnerability. In this research, we searched Scopus Indexed articles published in the last 11 years (between 2008 and 2020) using two keywords (“XSS attack prevention” and “XSS prevention”). The purpose of this study was to conduct a literature review on XSS prevention techniques e.g., strengths and weaknesses, including structural issues and real-time deployment location in order to extract valuable information. This review identified 14 articles among the 25 selected articles that provided various suitable prevention techniques for XSS attacks. Seven articles are based on tools that have been implemented and take into account design, coding, testing, and integrating validation processes, six articles are about server site solutions, and one is about automatic mitigation solutions. As a result, this research will be invaluable in guiding the advancement of XSS prevention techniques.

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1. INTRODUCTION

Web applications are a mandatory requirement for businesses, organizations, and customer-behavior solutions in order to provide easy access and improved performance to their target users in modern life. Security is a major concern in web applications since they contain personal data and information about people. The most common web application vulnerabilities, as per the open web application security project (OWASP) are injection, broken authentication and session management, cross-site scripting (XSS), broken access control, security misconfiguration, sensitive data exposure [1]. XSS is a client-side code injection attack that allows an attacker to execute malicious JavaScript in the browser of another user by injecting vulnerable web application pages. When a random user visits the compromised page, the page will deliver the malicious script into the victim's browser and execute it. Three types of XSS attacks and their removal techniques are; (i) an attacker injects a malicious script which is permanently stored on the targeted database server-stored XSS vulnerability; (ii) users also inject XSS attacks via phishing emails and other websites

when they get a request from a crafted link, after clicking these links the injected code reflects the attack to the user's browser – reflected XSS attacks or XSS Type-I attack; (iii) document object model (DOM) based XSS simply means an XSS vulnerability that appears in the DOM instead of the HTML part which occurs when a page is managing an action or performing any specific transactions [2]-[5].

XSS attacks should be intensely managed for security purposes. During the research, we observed that the majority of the proposed models and implemented tools or techniques are intended to identify and prevent only one or two types of XSS vulnerabilities. It should be noted that while these tools can prevent XSS vulnerabilities, they face obstacles in reducing the attack rate. Therefore, the goal of the study was to assist users in gaining an independent understanding of the existing XSS vulnerability prevention mechanisms as well as their strengths and weaknesses. This article also discussed the deployment location of the XSS vulnerability in web applications.

The remainder of this paper is laid out as; section 2 implies some relevant research works; section 3 provides details of the methods of this research. Result, evaluation, and discussion are outlined in section 4. And finally, the paper is wrapped up in section 5.

2. RELEVANT RESEARCH WORKS

Tariq *et al.* [6] proposed utilizing genetic algorithm (GA) in conjunction with threat intelligence and reinforcement learning (RL) to defeat XSS attacks, with the results being not only more flexible to changes in XSS payloads, but also more understandable to end-users. Rao *et al.* [7] examined XSS and its taxonomy including XSS attack devices, as well as analysis and prevention of XSS forgeries. Kumar *et al.* [8] suggested a unique method called obfuscation to safeguard online applications from SQL injection attacks, XSS attacks, and reverse engineering attacks. A comprehensive analysis of XSS exploitation as well as existing detection and prevention mechanisms are discussed in [9]. Stency and Mohanasundaram [10] compared XSS attack detection techniques in terms of algorithm simplicity, algorithm type, and performance metrics. Vital data on the operations of machine learning (ML), predictive analytics, and the development of the significant web that properly evaluates and eliminates SQL injection attack (SQLIA) with experiential value demonstrated in the receiver operating curve and Confusion matrix was provided in [11].

The goal of the work Gogoi *et al.* [12] was to measure the efficiency of various ML algorithms in identifying XSS attacks in web apps and websites, as well as to utilize ML to detect XSS attacks through various ML methods. Kumar *et al.* [13] described a multi-layer prevention approach in which the attacker is defended at the API key authentication level using an encryption technique that prohibits the attacker from gaining direct access to the API. Google's secure-by-design engineering approach was proposed in [14] which successfully avoids DOM-based XSS vulnerabilities in large-scale web development. Ivanova and Rozeva [15] proposed an ML technique for detecting stored XSS attacks and defending a representational state transfer (REST) web service written in JAVA, which was evaluated in a specifically designed test-bed simulation environment that included the IntelliJ IDEA environment, Postman, and a web browser. A secure framework that may be used to accomplish real-time detection and mitigation of XSS attacks in cloud-based web applications via deep learning (DL) at a high level of accuracy was presented in [16]. A solution integrating three techniques to determine the most difficult attacking challenges is revealed in [17] by implementing Random Forest (RF), k-Nearest Neighbors (k-NN), logistic regression (LR), support vector machine (SVM) algorithms, content security policy (CSP) approach, web application firewall (WAF), intrusion detection and prevention system (IDS and IPS). Maurel *et al.* [18] investigated utilizing neural networks to identify XSS vulnerabilities utilizing static methods.

3. METHOD

3.1. Article search process

We performed a methodical search strategy to find the publications that detail how XSS vulnerabilities in web applications are exploited. In our methodical search proceeding, we searched with two keywords from the Scopus Indexed databases to evaluate the article. We began by searching for publications published between 2008 and 2021 using the term "XSS attack prevention" and "XSS prevention".

3.2. Article inclusion and exclusion criterion

We employed a set of criteria to add and reject articles from the batch of articles discovered through Scopus indexing database search. Then we studied the title, abstract, methodology, and findings of each article to determine which ones to include and reject from the list of papers obtained by our systematic searching process and only articles that were utilized to avoid XSS attacks were considered.

3.3. Data extraction

Each article was assessed based on the following key points: (i) performance comparison of different types of XSS attack, (ii) overview of three types of XSS vulnerability detection and prevention techniques, (iii) deployment location of XSS vulnerability in web applications.

3.4. Defensive coding

The defense code mechanism is performed in three stages as shown in Figure 1. The XSS prevention strategies were chosen first, followed by various XSS defense code techniques. Finally, injected locations have been identified using defense coding techniques. Figure 2 presents the categorization of defense coding mechanism. An updated methodology of XSS prevention for cloud platforms was given in [19] which first scans HTTP requests for embedded URI links that point to URLs of external JS files containing malicious XSS payloads. Exact taint tracking and coarse-grained both are implemented with JavaScript, and the researchers illustrate how the precise taint tracking API may be used to fight against XSS attacks and SQL injection [20]. Dembla *et al.* [21] offered a client-side solution using a knapsack cryptographic local proxy with encryption and decryption functionality to protect cookies against XSS attacks. This solution encrypts the cookie's value (session-ID) attribute at the cryptographic local proxy before delivering it to the browser, and then sends the encrypted cookie's requests to the cryptographic local proxy, which decrypts them and forwards them to the web server. A new approach to thwart XSS attacks was presented in [22] which is independent of the languages used to construct web apps and solves XSS vulnerabilities that originate from different interfaces. The approach is structured, configured, and constructed in .Net, XML, and XSD, then tested in a web application written in JSP/Servlets and deployed in the JavaBeans Open-Source Software (JBOSS) application server. It is determined to be effective since it allows for cross-language use with very little configuration to prevent XSS. A context-sensitive encoder is derived from context-free grammars in order to serve appropriate unparsing of potentially malicious input data for all context-free languages [23]. This unparsing process produces documents in which the input data has no effect on the structure of the document and has no effect on its intended semantics.

Figure 1. The architecture of defense coding mechanism

Figure 2. Categorization of defense coding mechanism

Wang *et al.* [24] proposed a dynamic detection framework (TT-XSS) for DOM-XSS using taint tracking at the client side which involved rewriting all JavaScript features and DOM APIs to taint browser rendering. To this purpose, additional data types and methods are introduced to enhance the original data structure's semantic description capabilities, based on which the taint traces were evaluated during page parsing by tainting all sources, sinks, and transfer processes. The Knuth-Morris-Pratt (KMP) string matching technique was used to compare the user's input string with the stored pattern of the injection string in order to detect any malicious code in [25]. Gupta *et al.* [26] offered a context-sensitive solution based on static taint analysis and pattern matching techniques, with an implemented prototype tool validated on a public data set of 9408 samples, to detect and remediate XSS vulnerabilities in web application source code. Guaman [27] offered a tool that allows testing and validation procedures to reduce vulnerabilities and make web applications secure using a REST architectural style, a design pattern facade, and Java EE from the aspect of design, development, and deployment.

After studying these articles, we can conclude that a defensive coding mechanism is a type of defensive design that works in the event of a failure, especially when high availability, safety, or security are required. It aims to increase the overall quality of software and source code by making the source code accessible and by ensuring that the software performs appropriately in the face of unexpected inputs or user actions.

4. RESULTS, EVALUATION AND DISCUSSION

4.1. Search article results

Figure 3 summarized the search results of the articles. Based on the phrase cross-site scripting attack, we discovered 81 publications published in renowned journals and conferences between January 2008 and December 2021 using our systematic article search process. Then we scanned all of the articles in detail, identifying the most important points in each. We used two keywords to find the publications: "XSS Attack Prevention" and "XSS Prevention," which yielded 10 and 15 articles, respectively. We next studied each article's title, abstract, keyword, and technique before selecting 14 publications for analysis from the Scopus Indexed Databases. As a result of this search, 14 publications were found that explored the XSS vulnerability prevention technique in web applications.

Figure 3. The process of article searching

4.2. Descriptive analysis

Table 1 summarizes the findings of the 14 articles on XSS attack prevention strategies. We discovered a method that can automatically insert borders and establish policies to mitigate the attacking probability of an XSS vulnerability [28]. To safeguard the web application from XSS attacks, an execution flow analyzer has been built that can emulate client program behavior [29]. A browser proxy has been designed to secure the security of sensitive data using an information flow approach [30]. A server-side approach has been implemented in some research that limits user input from untrusted sites, removes the no-output script, and readily accommodates complicated attacks [31]-[35]. Several researchers have produced some technologies that can reduce XSS attacks from online applications by taking into account design, coding, testing, and incorporating validation [26], [27], [36]-[38].

Table 1. XSS attack prevention technology summary

Authors	Tools	Strength	Weakness
Gupta <i>et al.</i> [26]	XSSDM	XSS vulnerabilities are precisely detected and mitigated using taint analysis and pattern matching techniques	It is necessary to improve support for the object-oriented paradigm
Guamán <i>et al.</i> [27]	RESTful WS	To reduce flaws and strengthen the security of web applications through design, development, and deployment while taking testing and validation into account	Security and software development standards should be set to ensure the system's integrity
Shahriar and Zulkernine [28]	S2XS2	Create policies and dynamically insert borders	Time-consuming and low detection capability
Chen <i>et al.</i> [29]	An execution flow analyzer	Create the FSA in order to simulate the client program's actions	Need to modify the web source code
Xiao <i>et al.</i> [30]	information flow	The security of sensitive data is ensured by using JSTFlow as a browser proxy	There are restrictions to the sensitive data that has been detected
Barhoom and Kohail [31]	server-side solution	Prevent untrusted user input, modify the trusted code structure	Retrieve from the accessible network's server
Bisht and Venkatakrishnan [32]	XSS-GUARD	Define the server-side code and eliminate the no-output code	Do not forbid the permissible benign HTML
Mewara <i>et al.</i> [33]	XSS-ME	Easy accommodation of complex attack	Can detect and prevent only one attack
Caliwag <i>et al.</i> [34]	escaping technique	Capable of preventing XSS attack on the created online inventory system by removing unnecessary data	XSS attack mitigation was the sole focus
Maurya [35]	'Positive Security Model' based 'Server-side solution'	Allow safe tags from the blacklist to perform XSS with faster time processing when matching attack vectors	Attackers can circumvent the input sanitizer though it will be blocked later
Gupta and Gupta [36]	XSS-SAFE	Sanitization routines are injected into the JavaScript source code to detect and mitigate maliciously injected XSS attack vectors	Only recognizes the link between stored and injected features in the JavaScript source code
V <i>et al.</i> [37]	BIXSAN: browser independent XSS Sanitizer for prevention of XSS attacks	HTML parse tree producer is used to improve the inconsistency of web browser performance along with to recognize static script tags	Unable to detect XSS of dynamically growing parsing quirks in the XSS cheat sheet as the method evaluated by referring to it
Saxena <i>et al.</i> [38]	FLAX: systematic discovery of client-side validation vulnerabilities in rich Web applications	A lightweight tool in comparison to others, with no false positives and sufficient scalability	The complexity of sanitization failures that persist in client-side javascript code has not been highlighted in FLAX testing
Wurzinger <i>et al.</i> [39]	SWAP: mitigating XSS attacks using a reverse proxy	Strong detection of differences between benign and injected javascript code	Many types of XSS attacks are undetectable

4.3. Evaluation based on the attack type

As stated in Table 2, we investigated and evaluated each recommended strategy to see if it might be used to counteract a specific attack. We conducted an analytical evaluation based on our experience because we were unable to assess any of the methods in real-time practices due to the lack of implementation codes for most methods. Except for DOM-based XSS, we found five articles regarding tools developed for server-side XSS attacks that can detect stored and reflected XSS [26], [28], [33], [40], [41]. Four articles discussed how their implemented tool can only detect stored XSS in server-side web applications [31], [36], [42], [43]. Only reflected XSS can be detected by two studies that are deployed for server-side location [32, and 37]. Three studies highlighted how their tools can detect reflected and DOM XSS from server-side locations [25], [44], [45]. Five studies that are deployed for client-side location can only identify DOM XSS [24], [29], [30], [46], and [47]. A tool for detecting stored XSS in client-side web applications was developed in a study [38]. A study developed a client-side tool capable of detecting both stored and reflected XSS [39]. In a paper, techniques were created to detect stored XSS on cloud-based online applications [48]. A study developed a tool for detecting reflected XSS in client-side web applications [49].

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Table 2. Evaluation based on the attack type

Authors	Deployment location	Stored XSS (persistent)	Reflected XSS	DOM XSS
Wang <i>et al.</i> [24]	Client-side	N	N	Y
Abikoye <i>et al.</i> [25]	Server-side	N	Y	Y
Gupta <i>et al.</i> [26]	server-side	Y	Y	N
Shahriar and Zulkernine [28]	Server-side	Y	Y	N
Chen <i>et al.</i> [29]	Client-side	N	N	Y
Xiao <i>et al.</i> [30]	Client-side	N	N	Y
Barhoom and Kohail [31]	Server-side	Y	N	N
Bisht and Venkatakrishnan [32]	Server-side	N	Y	N
Mewara <i>et al.</i> [33]	Server-side	Y	Y	N
Gupta and Gupta [36]	server-side	Y	N	N
V <i>et al.</i> [37]	server-side	N	Y	N
Saxena <i>et al.</i> [38]	Client-side	Y	N	N
Wurzinger <i>et al.</i> [39]	Client-side	Y	Y	N
Gupta and Gupta [40]	Server-side	Y	Y	N
Gundy and chen [41]	server-side	Y	Y	N
Agten <i>et al.</i> [42]	server-side	Y	N	N
Shahriar and Zulkernine [43]	server-side	Y	N	N
Shrivastava <i>et al.</i> [44]	server-side	N	Y	Y
Cao <i>et al.</i> [45]	server-side	N	Y	Y
Pan and Mao [46]	Client-side	N	N	Y
Weinberger <i>et al.</i> [47]	Client-side	N	N	Y
Gupta and Gupta [48]	Cloud	N	Y	Y
Stamm <i>et al.</i> [49]	Client-side	N	Y	N

** “Y” indicates a method that can successfully stop an attack of that type and “N” indicates a method that cannot stop an attack of that type.

4.4. Evaluation based on deployment

Table 3 presents an analysis of each approach based on different deployment requirements. Three methods are highly resistant to attacks: cryptography, exception management, and parsing. Pattern matching, HTML escaping, JavaScript escaping, and ML are four techniques that are moderately resistant to attack, whereas the XML approach is not.

Table 3. Evaluation based on deployment requirements

Method	URL	Login	Search	Detect	Prevent	Modify code base	Resistant to attack
Cryptography	N	Y	N	N	Y	Y	High
Pattern matching	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	N	Medium
XML approach	Y	Y	Y	N	Y	N	Low
Exception management	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	N	High
HTML escaping	Y	N	Y	Y	N	N	Medium
JavaScript escaping	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	N	Medium
Machine learning	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Medium
Parsing	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	High

** “Y” indicates the method can be deployed to that injection parameter and “N” indicates the method cannot be deployed to that injection parameter.

5. CONCLUSION

In this paper, we presented a case study on the prevention of XSS vulnerabilities in web applications. We classified various types of defense coding techniques based on XSS prevention methods. Furthermore, based on the deployed locations, we discussed the strengths, weaknesses, comparison, and evaluation of various types of XSS prevention techniques. The points raised during our discussion will be useful in making a decision about implementing XSS prevention tools to protect web applications from XSS vulnerability exploitation. Moreover, we have concentrated on research directions and challenges related to XSS prevention techniques. Although several techniques for preventing XSS attacks have been implemented, their usage for real-time deployment location and extraction of estimated useful information may still be endangered by the issue emphasized in this study.

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